

Structural Transformations in Khasi Folktale Adaptations: From Oral Narrative to Cinematic Storytelling

Paper ID: 21331 | Submission Date: 2026-03-02 | Acceptance Date: 2026-03-23 | Publication Date: 2026-03-25

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19369432

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Abstract

Oral narrative is an important means of communicating indigenous knowledge, customs and history. Folktales in the Khasi society in Northeast India serve as a medium of narrating stories that conveys moral values to the community along with explaining social and cosmological values. With the advent of cinema, the folktales that have been narrated in the community for generations are being adapted into films, thereby changing the way folktales are narrated. This paper examines the ways in which indigenous oral narrative structures change when folktales are adapted into films by analysing two films, *Manik Raitong*, directed by Ardhenu Bhattacharya (1984) and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem*, directed by Kamki Diengdoh (2009) based on Khasi folktales. The paper draws upon orality studies, structuralism, post-structuralism, and adaptation theory and examines how the plots are developed, character representation, thematic elements highlighted and moral values emphasised. It analyses the ways in which audiovisual techniques such as visual communication and narrative structures are adopted in films and how they alter the indigenous oral narrative structure by turning the symbolic oral narrative into a visual and dramatic medium thereby engaging the contemporary audiences. The paper will exemplify how the indigenous folktales are modified when they are transported across different media forms while at the same time maintaining a strong connection with culture.

Keywords

Khasi Folktales, Oral Tradition, Film Adaptation, Indigenous Cinema, Structuralism, Post-Structuralism, Folklore and Film.

Introduction

In many Indigenous cultures, oral storytelling was an important cultural way of passing on knowledge, values and customs to younger generations. Oral narrative unlike literature is performance and interaction. It is a dynamic form which is constantly evolving, created and negotiated between the storyteller and the audience during the communicative process. Oral narratives often depict aspects of indigenous worldviews, modes of behaviour, ecological knowledge and social structures that define Indigenous culture. According to Ong, oral culture narratives provide one of the major structuring devices, and that "storytelling is an art of memory, a social activity" (Ong 1982, p.139).

Oral traditions constitute an indispensable part of Khasi communal life and indigenous knowledge system prevalent among the Khasi people residing in the North-Eastern part of India since time immemorial. Folktales, myths and legends tell us numerous roles and functions beyond the simple entertainment value provided to society through imparting knowledge regarding cultural values, social norms and cosmology prevalent in society. These stories are narrated by the old men and women in the domestic or communal space, which is called *Sawdong ka Lyngwiar Dpei*¹. The narration of stories for the young generation plays a great role in generating participation, introspection, and critical analysis of society in relation to storytelling. Most of the scholars believe that the oral performances of indigenous people were the primary means of knowledge sharing as literacy rates are usually low in such communities, as pointed out by Nongbri (2000).

The continuity of oral traditions is threatened by the impact of modernisation, urbanisation, and globalisation on indigenous societies. Many Indigenous communities are moving from oral communication systems for knowledge sharing to written and digital forms. As Ong (1982) suggests, in moving from an oral base to a technological base, a number of important changes occur in the way that narratives are constructed and communicated in very different ways from

those of the oral tradition. In response to changing conditions in their cultures, Indigenous people are beginning to creatively exploit new media technologies to develop new indigenous languages, genres, and narratives for storytelling and knowledge sharing.

Film is one of the media forms that have quickly become highly significant for Indigenous communities across the world. Many communities are using film as a vehicle to narrate their culture and to re-explain it to themselves and others, thereby reinterpreting their traditional myths, stories, and legends in a modern medium. Ginsburg (2002) terms Indigenous film as cultural self-representation. By producing their own films, communities can reclaim the right to tell the stories of their culture, history, and identity. Where films of Indigenous communities have previously been merely a visual record of their customs, the Indigenous films are a new interpretation of their culture, using the new forms of visual storytelling to communicate the connections they have with their past and present.

It is quite obvious that an oral story would undergo many changes in the filmmaking process. The challenge lies in changing the way the story is narrated so that it fits into the film structure. An oral story may contain the necessary elements to maintain audience interest while telling a story orally, but these elements are not necessarily suited for the film structure, which typically involves more straightforward development of a plot, more fully developed characters, and more visualized depictions of conflict. As Bordwell and Thompson (2008) describe:

“Classical Hollywood storytelling usually uses a causal narrative structure, organizing events into a story about the activities and motivations of characters and leading to a conclusion that completes the story.” (p-94-95)

So, in order to transform an oral story into a film, the story undergoes a very different transformation.

In the context of narrative analysis, some scholars have adopted structuralist and post-structuralist theories. Some structuralist scholars such as Claude Lévi-Strauss and Vladimir Propp claim that old stories are always made up of the same structures, elements and oppositions that give meaning to these stories (Strauss, 1965; Propp, 1968). They assert that folktales are systems that represent the structure of culture through the relationships between the elements in a narrative. On the other hand, some post-structuralist scholars such as Roland Barthes and Jacques Derrida hold that the structures and elements that make up a narrative cannot be fixed, but the meaning of a narrative can vary depending on culture and medium (Barthes, 1977; Derrida, 2021).

Folklore deals with application of cinematic theories to the cinema of Meghalaya with special reference to folk culture. This paper analyses films like *Manik Raitong* (1984) and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* (2009) based on folktales and the manner in which they are interpreted and re-shaped into film form. It seeks to illustrate how the narrative structure, part of an oral tradition, is reworked to suit the aesthetic and temporal features of cinema.

The paper aims to situate film texts within the structuralist, post-structuralist and the indigenous media studies theoretical frameworks, in order to determine the ways in which indigenous oral narratives can be renegotiated in the new media age and the resultant impact on indigenous communities. Instead, by using cinema as a new genre to narrate indigenous oral traditions, we seek to establish the fact that the Khasi oral tradition has opened up spaces for articulation through cinema.

Objective of study

1. To examine the transformation of Khasi oral folktales into cinematic narratives in *Manik Raitong* and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem*.
2. To analyze how cinematic storytelling reshapes the structure and meaning of traditional narratives through structuralist and post-structuralist perspectives.

Review of Literature

3.1 Oral Tradition and Indigenous Knowledge Systems

It is generally accepted in folklore studies that folk narrative is a living form of cultural expression that has the ability to change and evolve as it is transmitted from one context to another through a variety of media. Dundes (1955) argues that because of this adaptability a folk narrative can only continue to act as a vital cultural form as long as it contains sufficient folk elements. So when a Khasi folktale is adapted from an oral form of storytelling to the film form it is simply continuing on in its evolution as a living cultural form of folktale. The folktale, as a cultural form, is transmitted from one context to another while retaining links with the culture of origin. In this way, the film form becomes just another means of relaying a valuable piece of

cultural heritage to a modern-day audience while at the same time acting as a tool for the preservation of the cultural links between the audience and the original folk tale.

The interest in oral traditions in academic circles suggests that they are vital to the culture's repository of knowledge and to its memory. Oral forms of communication differ from written forms in that the act of storytelling functions within a performance context, and the narrative is reproduced in a communicative interaction between the narrator and the audience. Ong (1982) refers to the characteristics of oral cultures as being accumulative, participatory and situational. In other words, the narrative is increased and elaborated each time it is recounted. So oral storytelling is not a pastime activity, but a very important institution for the preservation and transmission of cultural values, historical facts and social norms between generations.

Battiste (2008) identifies a number of roles that are performed by Indigenous oral stories. Roles that are identified include the retention of ecological knowledge, moral standards and the cosmology of Indigenous peoples. Indigenous knowledge is holistic and relational; it embraces cultural, environmental and spiritual elements, and is typically embedded within the Indigenous oral narrative tradition. Oral traditions have often encoded the body of knowledge referred to as traditional ecological knowledge (Berkes 1999).

Folklore of tribal oral traditions have been discussed in great detail in respect of Northeast India. The region is characterized by rich cultural traditions that sustain the tribal identities. As regards to Khasi tribe of Meghalaya, Nongbri (2000) asserts that folklore, oral tradition, ritual songs and myths are one of the major tools of communication for values and are used as genealogical records. Khasi folktales also project the matrilineal society prevalent in the Khasi society and their relationship with nature. So the Khasi folktales are a cultural record and also an educational tool, imparting moral values which guides the collective behaviour of the community.

Oral traditions are under threat from the forces of globalisation, urbanisation, and other factors like the rise of new media. According to Shinam and Raj (2025), young people in Indigenous communities are increasingly falling away from passing on knowledge through the traditional art of storytelling, because formal education values literacy and text over the oral. This paper therefore, highlights the academic quest to find ways of safeguarding and revitalising the oral through the use of new media technologies.

3.2 Film and Indigenous Storytelling

In recent years, visual media has become an important way to express Indigenous people's versions of history and culture and to promote Indigenous myths and legends. Scholars in the field of Indigenous media studies argue that Indigenous people use the medium of film in order to record their history and culture, but also in order to creatively express and communicate their stories. Ginsburg terms this Indigenous practice of media production as cultural activism. In this respect, the Indigenous people proactively engage with the mainstream media, and they also produce their own media, in order to ensure that they themselves are in charge of presenting their history, culture and mythology.

Film is one of the few media that can transfer an oral narrative to written or audiovisual form while making use of the performance elements of the oral tradition itself, such as gesture, intonation and the environment of the performance. As Hafstein (2008) mentions, audiovisual media can be used to safeguard intangible cultural heritage and to retain the performative aspects of the oral tradition. So, film is not a narrative about the oral tradition, but allows the audience to relive the performance of the oral tradition.

Films made by indigenous people around the world are using traditional storytelling but in new languages and visual frameworks. The diversity of films made by the Māori film industry in New Zealand and how they incorporate indigenous mythologies in film for young people that reflect their indigenous identity. It also examines how Native American filmmakers are using cinema to challenge the dominant perspective and to present their indigenous worldview and cultural perspectives to deal with issues within the Native American communities, Smith (2013).

Indigenous cinema as a category is not a subject of great scholarly discussion in India. Moreover, discussions of Indigenous cinema with regard to Northeast India are almost non-existent. While a substantial amount of work has been done on tribal folklore of North-East India and documentation of tribal oral traditions and myths, few works engage with the fact that myths and traditions are being reworked and reinterpreted in the visual medium of cinema. This is significant, since many regional film industries in India are utilising indigenous folklore in their films. Thus, engagement with indigenous cinematography is required.

3.3 Narrative Structure and Structuralist Approaches

Much work on narrative structure has been done within a structuralist framework, seeing narrative as a system composed of recurring elements within a narrative and within different narratives. According to Lévi-Strauss, the similarity of the structure of myths in different cultures comes from their use of the same fundamental symbolic oppositions, and myths provide a kind of release in the form of symbolism for universal social forces such as the struggle between culture and nature and between society and disorder (Strauss, 1965). Myths and folktales form a kind of symbolic system which deals with basic social conflict.

As Propp, 1968, explained there are a number of actions whose narrative function is always the same. A hero may leave home, encounter danger, and overcome it. Propp analyzed numerous folktales and concluded that narrative functions are often the same, regardless of their content. Clearly there is a common language that transcends cultures.

The structuralist method has often been applied in folklore studies to uncover cultural structures through forms, contents and patterns of stories. A certain number of Khasi folktales present structural oppositions which range from man's struggle with the conflicting claims of his private ego and of the social norms to man's struggle with the forces of nature or the supernatural. The pattern of such structural oppositions forms the core of the narrative structure of these tales and is used to depict the cultural values of the society. According to the structuralist literary theory, every narrative can be considered as a formal system which has an invariant message at every level and in this sense is semantic. The structuralist approach to narrative has been challenged. An objection to the structuralist view is that oral literature cannot be a formal system with an invariant message if the narrative is altered on each occasion of recitation in order to suit the audience to whom it is being told.

3.4 Post-Structuralism and Narrative Reinterpretation

Post-structuralism developed as a reaction to the structuralist critique. The post-structuralist theory expressed instability in cultural texts and how the meaning of those texts could change. Barthes, 1977, argued that because a text can be interpreted differently by readers in different cultural settings, there are multiple readings of a story possible. Différance, as explained by structuralist critic, Derrida (2021), also emphasizes the instability of the meaning of words within a language structure.

In this sense, the passing from an oral text to the cinematographic one is a moment of great importance in the interpretative process. In fact, when passing from one sign to another, the semantic content is reinterpreted in the context of the target code, and this also happens when an oral text is adapted into a film, as affirmed by Linda Hutcheon (2006) with the film adaptation theory, which denies the adapted text to be a simple copy of the original text, and instead considers it to be an interpretation of the latter and a new interpretative key.

For Indigenous oral storytellers, the flexibility of their stories may have held a different significance. When oral stories are translated and adapted into a visual language on the cinema screen, they must negotiate a new language and set of communicative and representational codes. These cinematic codes are the product of a range of discourses, including genre, cinematic style and the cultural politics of the time in which the film is made. Consequently when an oral story is translated and rendered on to the cinema screen it is open to multiple interpretations and the original meaning can be preserved or altered in some way.

Methodology

This paper employs qualitative comparative analysis to examine the transformation of Khasi oral tales into films. Two films, namely *Manik Raitong* and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem*, which are based on Khasi oral folktales, are chosen as the film adaptations for this paper.

The theoretical framework for this study is grounded in the principles of structuralism and post-structuralism. Structuralism, exemplified by the work of Vladimir Propp (1968) and also by Claude Lévi-Strauss (1965), considers that all the folktales that exist in the world, despite the differences that may be observed in various ethnic or geographical contexts, reflect a set of narrative structures and symbolic oppositions that reflect the cultural codes valid for each historical period. This approach enables us to check whether the cinematic adaptations preserve the narrative schemes of the oral narratives from which they were taken.

This study will employ comparative method to discuss the translation of narrative meaning from an oral narrative to its cinematic adaptation. In other words, the essential argument here is that while the film adaptation maintains the same narrative structure and elements as that of the oral narrative, these elements are interpreted differently by virtue of the distinct narrative language and cinematic style of film.

Analysis

4.1 Narrative Transformation from Oral Storytelling to Cinematic Form

The transition of oral storytelling to cinema shows a change of focus from the specific features of individual genres to the general transformations which occur when a mode of narrative is translated from one medium to another. The oral narrative is a type of oral poetry situated in a performatory context in which the relationship between the narrator, the audience and the narrative is reciprocal. It is transformed into a different genre when it is adapted to cinema and integrated into the form and the conventions of the film narrative, characterized by a plot which is cohesive and developing, the individuation of characters and a visual language instead of a verbal one.

Ong argues that narrative in oral cultures is

“more substantially compositional, more substantially episodic, more substantially situational than our usual ideas of narrative would lead us to suppose that is, more narrative in the ancient sense than in the modern. Oral narratives are good as they are told and retold and recited, again and again in different versions according to the fashion of the moment and with the ease of improvisation possible in a live oral setting and so develop in each telling” (1982, p-47).

The Khasi folktales of *Manik Raitong* and *U 'Suid Tynjang* which are adapted into *Manik Raitong* (1984) and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* (2009) bring to the forefront the transformation of these tales from their original form into cinema. These tales had their roots in the rich oral tradition of the Khasi community, where they were narrated for educational purposes. When the tales were transformed into films, the characters, the plot and the theme took centre stage.

Structuralism affords one of the most interesting approaches to understanding the way in which narratives change from one medium to another. Using Claude Lévi-Strauss's ideas as a basis, it is possible to argue that narratives based on myth or fairy tale contain opposing pairs of concepts that provide a structural framework, as the following list of pairs exemplifies: order/disorder, culture/nature, authority/transgression. Again, these are dealt with through the medium of symbolism in oral versions of the narrative, in the film versions of the same narrative, they are treated through characterisation and through the individualisation of the characters concerned, the development of their psychology.

4.3 Character Arcs and Narrative Structure in *Manik Raitong*

Manik Raitong is a very popular folktale among the Khasi people of Meghalaya. In its oral version, it is a classic tragic love story and a moral teaching about the prohibited love of two people belonging to different castes and classes. The *Manik Raitong* and *Mahadei² Lieng Makaw* episode brings out the impossible love between them and the tragic aftermath of Manik's rebellion against the aristocracy and the social norms and regulations thereof.

In the narrative framework of an oral narrative Manik and the *Syiem³* are not treated as fully-fledged human characters but as carriers of the meanings of the social forces they embody. Manik represents truthfulness, modesty and humanity and the *Syiem* represents power and social norms. The central action of the narrative is the struggle between these two opposing pairs of values. What is stressed in the narrative is not so much the consequences of the violation of these norms as the teaching inherent in the narrative concerning the sociomoral repercussions of such violation.

In the film adaptation the story of *Manik Raitong* has been transformed from a symbolic one to a more character-oriented narrative. The film form necessitates the audience's identification with the characters in the story so that they may act and be moved. So in the film adaptation, they focused more on the characters of Manik and Lieng Makaw.

Manik is a humble and unambitious hero who is made into a tragic hero of classical proportions and whose narrative career marks his progression from humble innocence to tragic fall and even as a fallen hero, the emotional impact is reduced to a pitiful level by the cold calculation of court politics. Manik and Lieng's internal emotions are shown through close-ups, musical motifs, and suspense and silence, which are not possible in oral narration.

In the film version, *Lieng Makaw* is developed into a more rounded and richer character. In the oral narrative, Lieng Makaw's role is purely that of a marker of social status. In the film adaptation, the struggle to reconcile her personal desires with society's expectations makes her one of the central characters. Her inability to make a decision at a few pivotal moments in the story, notably when the *Syiem* proposes marriage to her, adds a dimension of psychological complexity to her character which is missing from the oral narrative.

In the film version, the moral of the story is transformed. In the oral version the death of the heroine demonstrated the social order and therefore the moral of the tale. In the film version, the power of the *Syiem* is not a symbol of the social order, but a force that suppresses the free development of individuals. This is demonstrated by careful composition and emphasis of the main characters of the film and their love story, which heightens the audience's emotional reaction and the sense of injustice of the *Syiem*'s law and the tragic death of Manik.

The film in question takes the folktale as the basis and, through a new narrative composition, depicts a tragedy in a different manner, focusing not so much on the psychological states and behavior of the protagonists. Instead of interpreting the folktale as a pedagogical didactic narrative with a moral purpose in mind, the film renders it a tragedy and employs the tragedy genre to interpret the folktale in a completely different narrative fashion.

4.4 Horror, Fear, and Moral Instruction in *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem*

Although the film is based on the popular Khasi folktale of *U 'Suid Tynjang*, the monster of misfortune who represents all sorts of danger and evil and is always used as a cautionary tale to scare children and the public into behaving and making sure they are inside their homes before night falls.

In the context of oral tradition, this legend can be interpreted as an educational tale, focusing on the theme of interaction with the spirit world and exploring the notions of obedience, prudence, and respect for the boundaries that separate the domain of humans from that of supernatural beings. The purpose of this legend is not to terrorize the listener, but rather to transmit a message and to convey an educational lesson.

Cinema can change the genre of a story into anything it wants, and in this case, the film turned the story into a horror genre. This is an example of the power of cinema to elicit specific affects through the use of specific film devices. Carroll (2003) argues that horror films elicit fear and suspense in the audience through the depiction of fearful and unknown objects on the screen.

The use of low light, sound effects and montage editing all serve to heighten the dramatic tension of the story in *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem*. When the narrator's somewhat vague explanation of the ethereal *U 'Suid Tynjang* is played out on screen, the story shifts from being a moral warning to a more personal and dramatic experience.

Carroll (2003) and other film scholars have argued that a range of emotions are created in the audience in horror films, such as fear, suspense and anticipation. Fear is constructed through the depiction of the fearful, achieved through a visual representation of threats and the unknown that invades the everyday world of the main characters. In *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* the use of lighting, sound and editing is employed to evoke an emotion from the audience for the portrayal of the supernatural encounter. In the oral version of *U 'Suid Tynjang* the monster is purely a product of the imagination. The events that take place are merely described. In the film version of *U 'Suid Tynjang* the monster is given a physical form. The components and elements of the oral form are transformed into a visual format that evokes different emotions in the audience.

In the folktale the narrative form has to serve the didactic purpose; in the film form the narrative can unfold in a different way. The encounter with the supernatural is no longer a

didactic sign designed to underscore the moral of the tale, but a dramatic device that can be used to create suspense, horror and fear in the cinema audience. The film is an example of how a moral folktale can be transformed into a genre narrative and at the same time remain highly relevant to the culture in which it is shown.

4.5 Structuralism and the Narrative Transformation of Khasi Folktales

Saussure argued that it is not the individual elements of cultural artefacts that carry meaning, but the relationships they have with each other within a system (Saussure, 1983). Thus narrative structures can be seen as systems of codes, patterns, relations or structures of opposition and of functions.

Another narrative layer is added when we reflect on Strauss's argument about Carnival and the masks as a narrative that belongs to the world of myth and folktale, and when he brings into discussion the structural patterns of myths across cultures which inevitably include a system of binary oppositions: (life and death, nature and culture, order and disorder, etc.) through which the basic antitheses of human society are revealed, mediated through the medium of myths. For a more focused examination of the narrative structure, one can refer to Tzvetan Todorov, where he examines the elements of a narrative, and focuses on the underlying narrative structure, the message which the author transmits through the text.

Through a structural approach to the Khasi folktales of *Manik Raitong* and *U 'Suid Tynjang* the study reveals that cosmology, characters, events and plot structure in the tales embody the manifestation of structural binary oppositions which serve to convey the moral and social values embedded in the stories.

4.5.1 Binary Oppositions in Khasi Folktales

The structuralist view is that stories use the device of what they call 'binary oppositions' to give them meaning. The oral story of *Manik Raitong* illustrates well how the common theme of oral literature, the conflict between man's desire and the social order, works out in this medium. Manik, the main character, represents personal emotion and a man's right as an individual, while the *Syiem* represents the social aspect and the principle of status. There is no reconciliation possible between these two opposing ideas.

The opposition that we see in the story, is to do with the social conflict existing in traditional societies. In our society, individualistic desires are often sacrificed at the altar of social harmony. Manik's death in the story, restores the social balance. The structuralist view is that the story is not just a romantic tragedy, but a conflict between two opposing principles of the social order.

The folktale underlying the *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* is an example of a widespread genre of story that illustrates the basic themes of safety versus danger and of society in contrast to nature. In this case, the safety and morality of the village are set against the threat of danger and the mysterious and supernatural dangers of the forest at night. The boundary between the two worlds is violated when the curious child or disobedient child strays from the safety of parental and societal constraints and so falls prey to *U 'Suid Tynjang* or a monster in the woods.

Myths in which opposing moral values are contrasted with each other often express this contrast in terms of a geographical space, transforming the space into a symbol. We have already referred to this in the Khasi myths, in which the forest always stands for the margins of society, where the norms governing human behaviour are threatened.

4.5.2 Narrative Functions and Character Roles

According to structuralist narrative theory, there are universal narrative functions and character roles that recur across cultures. Propp (1968) after analysing a large number of Russian folktales, identified, that whether it is the same or different characters, the tales all follow the same sequence of narrative functions such as: (1) the departure; (2) the violation of rules or the performance of prohibited actions; (3) the notification or announcement of the violation; (4) the reaction to the violation and (5) the outcome or culmination of the tale.

In *Manik Raitong* the structural stages are presented in the same sequence as in the oral version. *Manik Raitong* begins with Manik and Lieng being in harmony with each other. The *Syiem* breaks this harmony by choosing Lieng to marry her, creating a disruption in the narrative. The love between Manik and Lieng, and their breach of the social hierarchy that governs relationships between members of different classes, ultimately lead to their being exposed and punished.

The tale is structured along the lines of the usual balance - disturbance - transgression - restoration of balance. Such a narrative structure is a feature of folktale genre used to teach and to reinforce social norms and values. The tragic punishment meted out to the illegitimate passion is used to confirm the validity of the social norms and hierarchy prevailing in a community.

The folktale of *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* also bears out this plot structure. The story opens with familiar tropes of people engaged in their everyday activities within a familiar village setting. The everyday world is breached when people venture into the forest at night, which is a place of danger and threat. It is in the forest that the encounter with the monster, in this case, occurs. The majority of the narrative then concerns the characters' attempts to survive the monster and kill it, so they can return to the relative safety of their world.

Although the events in the stories are quite different, they fit a typical pattern of a folktale that is common to many cultures. When one views the stories as compositions following the structuralist school of thought, one can see that they all follow a common narrative grammar.

4.5.3 Structural Transformation in Cinematic Adaptation

Even the most oral of traditions are bound to undergo some change when translated into film. Film as a medium tends to be more narrative driven and therefore the story, characters and setting all require more description in order to engage an audience. Bordwell and Thompson (2008) explain that in the classical cinema the principle that governs the organisation of events in the narrative is the principle of causal unity. This principle links the events of a film through the actions and goals of the characters and it uses the principle of plot structure to organize events in a way that forms a coherent and engaging whole.

In the story of *Manik Raitong*, the film adaptation stretches out and enriches the narrative framework that is strictly circumscribed in the oral form and brings to the foreground the daily life of the village, the interaction between the characters and the landscapes. It also investigates Manik and Lieng's emotional trajectory more closely, transforming the two characters who were more allegorical in the oral version into more humanised forms. This film adaptation introduces a number of changes in relation to the narrative structure and thematic ideas we have seen in the oral text. In an oral narrative, characters are often portrayed as one-dimensional representations of a moral concept. A film, however, is a medium that focuses on characters and on their emotional state. The basic structure of the main antagonism in the narrative is preserved in the film but it is now viewed through a more character-oriented prism rather than through the symbolic function of simple moral concepts.

The original oral tale of *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* is a straightforward cautionary story, but it is rearranged into a suspenseful plot with multiple characters and a sequence of terrifying events in the film adaptation. The editing, lighting and sound design all play a part in drawing attention to the divide between the relative safety of the home and the danger of the forest. The forest at night is a frightening environment visually and the monster is shown through the use of shadow, movement and sound effects. The film devices bring to life the symbolic battle that is at the heart of the story and allow the audience to participate in the tension on a deeply emotional level.

4.5.4 Structural Continuity and Narrative Transformation

In the present day, when values and social reality are undergoing considerable change, screenwriters have to make their stories relevant to contemporary social reality while maintaining the continuity of the traditional folktale, which is the basis of the screenplay for cinema films. As such, despite the film *Manik Raitong* and *Ka Miet Ka Jingtriem* adapting itself to the changing values and social reality, on the narrative plane, the fundamental antagonism between the opposites such as love and power, security and danger etc. that are inherent in the folktale sources of the two stories have been retained. In other words, while these films carry a whole range of new narrative and thematic content, the basic antagonism between the opposites has been treated as the framework for the narrative content of the cinema films derived from the folktale sources.

For the structuralist the transformation of Khasi folktales into cinema is no more than a change of structural form. Whatever the change in form, the symbolic oppositions, the narrative functions and the moral themes will remain the same. They will simply be transmitted in a different way.

Adaptation too demonstrates the narrative flexibility of forms across media. Oral narratives, literary works and films are all unique forms that impose very different formal constraints in order to organise the narrative structure of the original work in a way that preserves the integrity of the narrative and thus its meaning. When a narrative is adapted into another media form it must be transformed in order to fit the formal constraints of the target medium while at the same time preserve the original narrative structure and organisation.

4.6 Post-Structuralism and the Reinterpretation of Indigenous Narratives in Film

Post-structuralism is concerned with how meaning is generated by readers out of a text and its context, by the way the text is positioned in discourse (its discursive situation). So, although a tale might consist of a structured narrative and a particular pattern of oppositions at the structural level, as a narrative it is open to multiple interpretations as it travels through different social, cultural, media and reading contexts.

The Khasi folktales being translated into cinema form a very good example of this. When an oral narrative is translated or rather transformed into a film, it does not retain the narrative structure that was explained by the structuralist scholars. The medium of film, the language of cinema, and the social and cultural context of the time of the film impact and shape the narrative and its meaning. As Barthes (1977) mentions, the meaning of a text is not the one that the author intended. The meaning of the text is generated between the text and the reader. So when an oral narrative is translated into a film, it opens up numerous other meanings that were not available in the oral narrative.

This text, in the style of post-structuralist criticism, aims at highlighting the contradictions within a narrative structure which otherwise seems to possess formal unity and coherence. The oral narrative of *Manik Raitong* is taken as an example to demonstrate this phenomenon. The apparent social and moral order of the narrative is sustained by the tragic fate of Manik. Through the structuralist perspective, we find that the narrative resolves the contradiction between the individual's desire for change and the social order by validating the latter. The film complicates the previous reading. By using a series of visual and narrative tropes that frame Manik and Lieng as two star-crossed lovers separated by societal prohibition on illicit love, the film solicits the audience's emotional identification with the tragic fate of the young lovers. At the same time, the film's representation of the *Syiem* functions to undermine the initial representation of his role as a harmoniser of society and the upholder of social morality. Through specific visual and composition and camera angles, the film's representation of the *Syiem* is transformed into an even more personal force, one that invades and disrupts the intimate emotional world of Manik and Lieng.

Derrida (2021) describes the phenomenon where meaning is deferred and changed within a text rather than being fixed within some structural framework. Thus when a folktale is adapted and turned into a film it can no longer be considered a medium for the original aim of a folktale: to convey a moral to the audience. Instead of reinforcing the social status quo the folktale, as a film, can be seen as a commentary on power relations and as an exploration of the dramatic consequences of the suppression of emotions.

In *Ka Miet Ka Jingriem*, *U 'Suid Tynjang* is retold in order to attain a social and cultural goal. Oral folktale as a genre is used to convey lessons and disseminate knowledge to the audience via imparting moral values which are expected to be adhered to in that particular community. In the story, *U 'Suid Tynjang*, the monster's punishment serves as a warning to curb undesirable acts prevalent in the community. For instance, the monster punishing people by capturing them and forcing them to scratch his back continuously is all because they strayed into the forest at night, is a story to caution them against trespassing into the forbidden forest, thereby establishing the boundaries between the sacred and the profane.

In this film, the interpretation of the supernatural being is not the same. The film uses a great deal of visual horror in order to portray the supernatural being as an object of horror and suspense. Although the moral of the story is still present, it is not the central theme of the film. The folktale has been adapted so that the main focus of the story is on the terrifying elements rather than the moral that is present in the original story. The horror elements are more apparent in *Ka Miet Ka Jingriem*. The concentration on darkness, as well as the sound effects and pacing, all give the horror a more cinematic quality that was not present in the oral rendition of the story. The spirits that are the main theme of the story are transformed from being a moral tool to being a filmic monster that instills fear and horror.

According to the post-structuralist perspective, cinema could be seen as a reinterpretation of the narrative aspect of the oral tradition. Each time a story is recounted, whether it be the

original performance or a retelling, it is transmitted through the lens of culture and technology of the era in which it is told. Therefore, when an oral tradition is re-translated into cinema, the audience is left with a different version of the story, a reinterpretation of the theme. The reinterpretation of the theme from the oral tradition to the cinema screen is not a simple translation from one medium to another, but rather a reinterpretation of the content itself.

Film adaptation of folktale is more than retention of an oral tradition as viewed through post-structuralist prism. Film adaptation of folktale acts as an agent of change in terms of cultural values, providing an avenue for dissemination of folktale in an era where the traditional method of narration through an oral medium has lost its glamour. The folktale films in this context serve the purpose of reinterpreting cultural values, providing a narrative tool through the medium of cinema and, in the process, helping disseminate Khasi cultural values by narrating folktale stories through the new medium. It acts as a tool of unifying the rural and urban populace through films that are of a different cultural flavour but appeals to the modern era sensibilities and at the same time conveys values and belief systems that are indigenous to the Khasi community.

Conclusion

The translation process involves an analysis of the adaptation which occur in the oral narrative structure of the folklores and its metamorphosis into the narrative structure of the cinema medium. It is known that the oral narratives undergo adaptation in the performance context as well as in the textuality of the oral narratives, and these adaptation increase when the oral narratives are translated into films. Although the narrative structures of the oral narratives are malleable and flexible in the performance context, these structures have to be remade and remoulded to correspond to the demands of the cinema narrative structures, in which the narrative structure has to follow a linear form of presentation and has to have concrete evidence of development of characters and conflict that can capture the audience's attention in the cinema hall.

The structuralist approach to this study has shown that the structural characteristics of the folk tales which are included in the story are preserved and even enriched in the film versions. The elements common to the folktales which deal with love, social status, fear of the supernatural and the punishment of crimes are all reproduced in the film versions. However, the elements which are derived from the folktales are reshaped and readapted in the context of film as an audio-visual medium, which uses a plot and drama in order to attract the audience and to provide a unique individual experience for the characters appearing on the screen.

The post-structuralist argument for cinema is that the traditional narrative does not survive unscathed from the shift from an oral narrative medium to a visual medium like film. The films can be seen as a reinterpretation of the cultural value embedded in a traditional narrative that is transformed and adapted so that it can be conveyed in a new language to a new mass audience in a different time period using the new medium of film.

To explore the transformation of Indigenous texts from an oral tradition into a film text, and to explore the links that the film text maintains with culture, this paper provides an example of how a Khasi folktale was adapted into film. While the film does not displace the oral tradition, it acts as a mediator of the folktale, enabling Indigenous cultural texts to be removed from their cultural context and disseminated through the dominant film apparatus, a mass medium that is ubiquitous to contemporary media culture.

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Footnote:

1. Oral stories told around the kitchen hearth
2. Queen
3. Chief